

LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IS THE NEED OF TIME

Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

Email: shahlo-70@mail.ru

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6535-0197>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828934>

Abstract: Today, teachers in educational institutions conduct lessons using modern technologies. Language learning today depends more on the language learner than on the teacher. In the article, the author provides information about several rules for learning English effectively.

Keywords: Language, foreign languages, English, teachers, modern technologies, educational technologies, language learning.

Introduction.

Today, life cannot be imagined without foreign languages. As the process of globalization accelerates, learning a foreign language is becoming the need of the hour. Today, to become a good specialist in any field, knowing English has become a simple requirement. When learning a foreign language, the question I asked myself was: "How can I learn a foreign language quickly? How can I speak a foreign language easily?" "What is the secret of learning a language quickly and being able to speak it quickly? Why do most of the students who have been studying a foreign language for four years without looking up, when they cannot say three or four words in the language without making a mistake, it has nothing to do with the language "Students studying in non-specialist fields are mastering the language wonderfully, spending 3-4 hours a week studying the language?" After many years of research, I realized that the problem lies in the approach to language learning. I'm learning a sixth language today because I've caught a lot of mistakes and I find it easier than ever. I understand better every day that learning a foreign language is not as difficult as we think. It is important to choose the easiest way to learn a foreign language. Today, in educational institutions, teachers conduct lessons using modern technologies. Learning a language today depends more on the language learner than on the teacher.

Strong passion

The most important thing for learning a language is motivation (enthusiasm), as it is in every area of life. Always ask yourself why I should learn this language and remember your purpose for learning the language whenever you are struggling or in doubt. The most important thing is to understand that everything is simple and not so difficult that you can learn a language, that you have no less place than others in learning a language. Once you have gained confidence in learning a language, you can start learning a language.

Daily training

Nowadays, many language courses organize a lesson for two hours one or two days a week, and a language learner who is busy with everyday life cannot spare time for the language on other days and usually forgets the topics of the previous lesson until the next lesson and learning this language slows down the process. Therefore, when learning a foreign

language of your choice, you should learn it every day, and the process of learning the language will be much faster as a result of daily repetition. Therefore, if you want to learn a language well, make a daily commitment to yourself; "I spend half an hour or an hour studying English every day, in any situation!". Only then will your chances of remembering the language increase dramatically.

- Type of abilities
- Linguists have divided the study of language into four major areas:
- Reading is the ability to understand a text read in a foreign language;
- Listening is understanding the text heard in a foreign language;
- Writing - the ability to write in a foreign language;
- Speaking - the ability to express your thoughts in a foreign language. In order to achieve these four things, it is important to master the three most important things: grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation.

Therefore, without mastering these three things, it becomes more difficult to learn a foreign language.

Which tools are convenient?

Now, let's analyze the ways to quickly learn these three things based on which tools:

1. Grammar. Usually, many students who are learning a foreign language get nervous when talking about grammar. Like it or not, the most difficult part of learning a language is grammar. That's why learning grammar is so important. Fear not, this too can be learned very easily. In our grammar lesson, thousands of rules that are not used even by the nations that speak that language are studied and memorized. The biggest problem in our education system is in these memorizations. By the time students graduate, they know thousands of rules of French grammar and phonetics by heart, but they can't make a more complex sentence in the language without making a mistake. Forget all about memorizing rules and learn only what you need in grammar; A rule that is memorized but not used when speaking the language is like buying a car, but parking it in the garage and walking a long distance to work. For example, I remember memorizing more than 80 incorrect verbs during English classes. However, only 30 of them are used. For example, the verb "sweep". I don't remember ever using this incorrect verb when speaking or writing in English. In learning any language, you should follow the simplest way. Also pay attention to: What is a simple sentence in English or French? Possessive+Cut+Complementary. So, learning the grammar used in these three parts of the sentence is enough to learn the language. The goal of learning any language is to be able to speak it. Therefore, study only the grammar topics that are necessary for everyday speaking. When learning French, we initially studied the 12 tenses, but in 90% of cases only the present, past and future tenses are used. For this reason, it is enough to learn the three necessary tenses. It is from this point of view that learning grammar will be about 80% easier for you. When studying grammar, after choosing the most important topics for the language, divide them into weeks. Spend a week on each topic and study one topic in depth during the week. As a result, in three months you will have a sufficient grammatical basis to be able to speak a foreign language, and as you can see, it is not as complicated as you think.

2. Learning vocabulary.

Here too, forcing yourself to memorize words for years is the most wrong method. During my school years, I made it my task to memorize 10 words every day. The problem was that I could not use these words when speaking French, many of them were not used at all in

everyday life and were quickly forgotten. Then I realized that this method is very wrong in gaining vocabulary in the language. Over time, I realized from experience that the easiest way to memorize words is to read more in the foreign language being studied. If you are learning English, read texts in your field of interest or books and magazines on the Internet rather than reading boring, irrelevant texts. Do not stop at the words that everyone does not understand, but when you come across unfamiliar words that you need to understand the meaning of the sentence, find a translation in the dictionary or services such as Google Translate and put it back in the notebook. If possible, try to read 3-4 pages of a text in the foreign language you are learning every day, and each time you find the translation of an unfamiliar word, write it down. Never try to memorize what you write, I usually don't even read back what I write. Our ability to remember is formed in such a way that if we see a word and just translate it, we will not remember it, but if we write it down somewhere, the brain emphasizes the importance of this thing and the word starts to stick in our memory. . As a result, a word that occurs 5-6 times in different texts will be memorized in an unforgettable way, and at the same time, we will learn in which context the word is used in which meaning.

Another benefit of reading a text in a foreign language every day is that we will strengthen our grammar base by seeing the grammar topics we have learned used in the text. The second successful method of memorizing vocabulary was explained by Tim Ferriss, a famous American scientist and the author of the book "The Four-Hour Work Week". According to Perato's theory, we spend only 20 percent of our time on the things we need in our lives, but 80 percent of the results we achieve are given by this 20 percent of effort. Tim Ferriss can speak seven foreign languages fluently. He explains the secret of language learning as follows: *"3 months are enough to understand 90% of a foreign language you want, but it takes 3 years to understand 95%."* So, perfect learning of the language requires a lot of hard work. So, according to Perato's theory, first of all, it is necessary to thank the 20% that gives 80% of the results. I will explain it now in simple language. When learning vocabulary, you should learn only the most frequently used words in the language. According to statistics, the 200 most used words in English account for half of all English correspondence. That's why when memorizing a dictionary, it is enough to memorize the most used words in the language. Then, it is enough to learn by adding words in the field you need. Here you can download a list of the most frequently used words in the foreign language you are learning. So, it is enough to determine the priority to learn the vocabulary and learn exactly what you need. Even then, try to write five sentences with each of the words from the list without memorizing the word in the vernacular. Every time you make a sentence with them, the words will technically start to be memorized and your vocabulary will grow. So, when speaking a foreign language, only about 1,000 frequently used words are used in 90 percent of cases, and the rest is enough for everyone to learn according to their field. For example, if a medical worker learns these 1000 words and another 1000 words related to the medical field, he can communicate freely in English in his field without any difficulties.

3. Pronunciation.

Every language has its own pronunciation. According to linguists, there are more than 150 sounds in total, and each language uses an average of 30 sounds. As a result, there is a huge difference in the pronunciation of the languages. For example, French nasal sounds are completely absent in our language. Unlike Uzbek and French, there is no "o" sound in Russian. Usually, after learning to read a language, the easiest way to improve your pronunciation is to

listen to the foreign language as much as possible. It is necessary to watch movies, listen to songs and various radio texts in this language. If you search in the Yandex system, you will find hundreds, if not thousands, of audio courses in English alone. Listening to them on your player or phone will make your understanding of the language easier and your pronunciation will continue to improve. When listening to a song in a foreign language, it can be used for another purpose. Find the lyrics of your favorite song in a foreign language and translate it into your language using a dictionary. As a result, you will not only fully understand the meaning of the song, but at the same time you will enrich your vocabulary, these words will be imprinted in your memory with your favorite song for a lifetime. Apart from these three things, one of the most important things in learning a language is immersion in the language environment. If you try to use as much foreign language material as possible, your language level will gradually improve. For example, put everything in a foreign language, from the programs of your simple phone to the operating system of your computer. Get information from the Internet only in a foreign language and try to hear it in a foreign language as much as possible when watching TV or listening to the radio. Use the popular social networks such as Facebook, Vkontakte, many news sites in the English version.

Sign up for forums and chats in a foreign language and try to actively participate in them in a foreign language. I remember very well that a few years ago, finding movies in a foreign language was quite difficult. Thanks to the technological progress of recent years, this has not become such a big problem. Recently, I wanted to watch some French comedy in French because the translation of French films into Russian is not good, and their mentality cannot be explained in Russian. Discs with only one movie are sold in any disc store in Tashkent today, and the audio of the movie on these discs is in at least two different languages, which allows you to watch movies in their original language with Russian subtitles at the same time. At the same time, today, almost all national Internet operators provide free and unlimited Internet to internal Tas-Ix sources. Tas-Ix has a lot of Torrent Trackers where you can easily download foreign language movies in good quality and in two or three different languages for free. The importance of repetition in learning a foreign language should not be forgotten. As they say, repetition is the mother of knowledge, repeating the grammar topic you learned every week one day after two weeks can serve to consolidate it and keep it in your memory better.

With whom do I speak a foreign language?

Naturally, the question may be: "Okay, I did everything you said. But what do I need to do to speak the language? Who can I talk to in a foreign language? How can I improve my speaking skills?" The answer lies in today's social networks. Today, it is very easy to make friends from the country of your language on Facebook. It is possible to correspond with them and later even exchange skype accounts. At the same time, forums and various chats have become an ideal place to communicate in a foreign language. Also, cultural centers and institutes opened by embassies in Tashkent should not be forgotten. Cultural evenings and debates are usually organized there, which allows you to speak a foreign language. It is enough to go and actively participate in these events. A few years ago, I took an active part in events at the French Cultural Center in Tashkent. In this cultural center, every Friday, a round table called "Cafe Hugo" was held. Over a cup of tea, the French and the Uzbek youth would talk and exchange ideas on various topics in French. At that time, many of my peers who knew a foreign language preferred to sit quietly and listen to others, fearing to make a mistake. We Uzbeks have such a mentality, we are a shy people, everyone is afraid of making mistakes. However,

psychologists have repeatedly proven that the easiest way to learn is by making mistakes. That's why you should try to speak a foreign language without being afraid of making mistakes, and you will understand your own shortcomings as a result of making mistakes, and then you will focus on correcting these shortcomings. Important to speak a foreign language without being ashamed of mistakes. I have also "meloned" several times in the past years for speaking a foreign language, and there were times when I was laughed at in front of the whole group. But, you know, if I didn't make those mistakes, if I didn't know my mistakes, I wouldn't be able to learn the language to the extent that I am today. Think for yourself, you are a participant of a certain event organized with foreigners, and the foreigner who is talking to you is speaking your language with difficulty and mistakes. In this case, you will not look down on him for his mistakes, on the contrary, because he is learning your language, you will respect him, you will be happy and you will understand his mistakes. So, while communicating with foreigners in their language, they will take it for granted that you make mistakes and will even be happy that you are learning their language. So don't be afraid to make mistakes.

Support speakers

Another way to make learning a language easier is with ready-made speakers or guides in the foreign language. Today, even on your simple smartphone, there are hundreds of foreign languages with ready-made phrases used in various situations. It is in these guides that you can memorize ready-made sentences used in the language. These phrases will make it much easier for you to speak a foreign language. You can change one word in each sentence learned in these conversation books and use it in different situations and with different meanings. As a result, there is an opportunity to speak a foreign language during various trips. I think I have explained to you as much as possible how to learn a foreign language easily. These are the conclusions that I have drawn from my several years of experience in this field. This means that today's training centers that promise to teach a foreign language in 3 or 6 months are not deceiving you, but with the right methodology, it is true. When it comes to learning a foreign language, it depends on you and only you today, rather than the educational centers and teachers. Thanks to technical progress, today confidence, passion and the right methodology are enough to learn foreign languages. If anyone has any other ideas about things that can make learning a foreign language easier, feel free to add to this article.

References:

- 1.Kharatova, S. (2022, November). The role of integrated education in teaching foreign languages. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).
- 2.Kharatova, S., & Khusanova, I. (2022). Problems Of Planning English Lessons. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(6), 214-217.
- 3.Kharatova, S. (2022). PERSONAL QUALITIES AND JOBS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 1(5), 51-55.
- 4.Kharatova, S. (2022). Modern Methods In English Language Teaching. Science and innovation in the education system, 1(6), 31-34.
- 5.Kharatova, S. (2022). METHODS OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING ENGLISH. BEST ENGLISH LEARNING TECHNIQUE. Академические исследования в современной науке, 1(16), 49-52.
- 6.Kharatova, S. K. (2022). Concept of Language and Speech. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 2(4), 115-117.

- 7.Ахматова, Х. Ш. (2017). Концептуальные основы разработки технологий воспитания средствами иностранного языка в техническом вузе. Современные инновации, (3 (17)), 41-42.
- 8.Kharatova, S. (2022, November). The role of integrated education in teaching foreign languages. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).
- 9.Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
- 10.Харатова, Ш. Х., & Садикова, М. Б. (2020). Эффективные способы изучения английского языка. Academy, (2 (53)), 33-35.
- 11.Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Tendencies of development of distance education in global transformation. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(10), 353-362.
- 12.Kharatova, S. (2022). The role of higher education institutions in the development of innovative projects and technologies. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 2(10), 128-130.
- 13.Kharatova, S. K. Goals And Tasks Of English Language Teaching. International Bulletin Of Engineering And Technology, 2(9).
- 14.Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Teach English For Spesific Purposes. THEORETICAL AND APPLIED SCIENCE, 11, 30.
- 15.Kharatova, S. (2022). Technologies For The Development Of Language Skills In English Classes. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(6), 20-24.

